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Abstract	This document presents summary of progress and preliminary results related to the task 4.2.

History of Changes

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0.1 (draft)	20 June 2025	The initial draft of the document is ready and ready for distribution between PERSEPHONE project partners to review
V0.5	20 July 2025	Updated the report after an internal review
V1.0	30 July 2025	Final version ready

Executive summary

This deliverable, D4.2, outlines the advancements made in Task 4.2, which focuses on high-precision autonomous navigation, alignment, and situational awareness at the mine face. These capabilities are essential for preparing autonomous drilling and excavation machines to operate accurately and safely in confined, unstructured underground environments. The task builds upon previous navigation work and targets the final stages of autonomous deployment where precise positioning and sensing are critical for mission success.

The deliverable addresses three core technical contributions:

1. **Autonomous Path Planning to the Mine Face:** A dedicated motion planning module is integrated within the STAGE autonomy framework to allow the deployer robot to navigate from a known global position to a mine-face location specified by an operator. This uses a specialized behavior in the STAGE behavior tree that considers the geometry of the tunnel and the operational footprint of the robot.
2. **Normal Vector-Based Alignment at the Mine Face:** Upon reaching the vicinity of the target location, the robot autonomously extracts geometric features from the LiDAR point cloud to compute surface normals of the tunnel face. These normals are used to align the robot perpendicularly to the wall, ensuring proper positioning for downstream operations such as drilling or inspection.
3. **Vision-Language Model (VLM)-Based Magnesite Detection:** The deliverable also introduces a novel perception module that leverages large-scale VLMs to semantically detect magnesite ore directly from RGB video streams. This modality-agnostic approach is designed to work in varying lighting and texture conditions without requiring extensive task-specific training data.

In addition to these, we present a preliminary evaluation of a radar-based odometry approach, which demonstrates promising results for enabling robust localization in environments where optical sensing is unreliable due to darkness, dust, or occlusions.

The work reported here marks a major step toward achieving perception-driven, infrastructure-independent, and mission-ready autonomous mining systems, and forms a technical foundation for further hardware integration in upcoming phases of the project.

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Table of content

Executive summary	3
Table of content.....	4
1 Abbreviations	5
2 Introduction	6
2.1 Purpose and scope of the document.....	6
2.2 Related documents.....	7
3 Technical Details	8
3.1 Methodology	8
3.1.1 Autonomous Navigation of the Deployer Machine to an Operator-Specified Mine Face	8
3.1.2 Graph-Based Multi-Robot Mission Control via the <i>stage_gui_plugin</i> 10	
3.1.3 Demonstration Setup for Operator-Specified Waypoint Navigation in Shared Map Context	13
3.1.3.1 Simulation-Specific Considerations	14
3.1.4 Global Path Planning to Operator-Specified Mine Face Using Shared Graph.....	15
3.1.5 Novel VLM-based segmentation of the mine face to accurately localize the magnesite ore concentration.	17
3.1.6 Precise navigation to the mine face considering the size and operational constraints of machines.....	23
3.1.7 Evaluation of multi sensor setup to demonstrate undisturbed operation in visually degraded environments.....	25
4 Partners Contributions:	44
5 Future Plans	45
6 Conclusions	46
7 References	47

2 Introduction

The present deliverable outlines the initial developments and integration efforts carried out under Task 4.2 – High-accuracy navigation and alignment for precise autonomous drilling & excavation operations. This task builds directly on the capabilities developed in Task 4.1, where autonomous machines navigate and explore the mine environment. While Task 4.1 primarily addresses the challenge of mapping and traversing large unknown areas, Task 4.2 focuses on the final, high-precision navigation and alignment stage, necessary before initiating drilling or excavation at identified mine faces.

In an operational mining scenario, it is essential that autonomous machines not only explore and reach regions of interest but also precisely align themselves to pre-defined target locations within tight spatial constraints. These targets may be newly discovered mine faces or pre-specified zones for drilling or material collection. Such end-stage navigation must be accurate, robust, and repeatable especially in degraded environments with dust, darkness, and limited structure.

In the initial phase of this task, efforts have focused on enabling the Deployer machine to receive spatial awareness data specifically the voxel map and the global graph from the *Explorer machine*. Using this shared global representation, the Deployer can compute a global route to a specific mine face waypoint. The goal position is selected manually by an operator within a 3D RViz2-based interface. Once the goal is confirmed, the Deployer autonomously follows a path through the previously mapped region, leveraging the graph generated by the Explorer and ensuring safe and efficient traversal through narrow and constrained drift segments.

This capability represents a significant step toward the realization of a fully autonomous drilling operation, wherein path planning, spatial reasoning, and high-precision final alignment are performed without the need for infrastructure or prior map availability. Additional modules related to fine alignment, obstacle consideration, and multi-sensor fusion are also being developed and will be detailed in subsequent sections of this document.

2.1 Purpose and scope of the document

The purpose of this document is to present the ongoing work and intermediate results under Task 4.2 of the project. Specifically, it documents the design, integration, and evaluation of the navigation and alignment capabilities that enable autonomous mining machines to reach and align with a specified mine face, in preparation for drilling or excavation.

The scope of this deliverable includes:

- Integration of the STAGE planner's waypoint navigation functionality for use by the Deployer machine.
- Use of shared voxel maps and global graphs from the Explorer machine to support long-range navigation.
- Implementation of a custom 3D goal selection interface in RViz2, allowing human operators to assign mine face targets.
- Autonomous global path planning and navigation through previously explored environments using the Explorer's global graph as reference.

While this deliverable focuses on the navigation-to-goal capability, complementary components such as vision-based alignment, machine positioning constraints and multi-sensor robustness in degraded environments are addressed in later sections and will complete the full pipeline for precision autonomous operation at the mine face.

2.2 Related documents

This deliverable builds directly on the outcomes and architectural definitions presented in D4.1 – Design and validation in simulated environments of novel path-planning and multi-machine coordination algorithms. D4.1 details the development of the STAGE planner [1], a graph-based navigation framework that enables autonomous machines to incrementally explore and map large-scale subterranean environments. A key aspect relevant to Task 4.2 is the STAGE planner's capability to generate and maintain both a global graph representation and a voxel-based map throughout the exploration process.

These data products produced by the *Explorer* machine form the informational backbone required by the *Deployer* machine to perform waypoint-based navigation. The global graph provides spatial connectivity between explored locations and frontiers, while the voxel map encodes local geometry and traversability. Understanding the mechanisms by which these structures are created, updated, and queried is essential for appreciating the navigation behavior demonstrated in Task 4.2. As such, D4.1 should be considered a foundational reference for the concepts, data structures, and algorithms employed in this task.

In addition to D4.1, this deliverable is also closely aligned with:

- System-level architecture and sensor integration which define the onboard sensing capabilities and localization frameworks employed by both the Explorer and Deployer machines.
- Task 4.3 and downstream work packages (WP5) that will build upon the navigation and alignment capabilities developed here to enable autonomous drilling, excavation, and coordination with additional robotic agents.

Together, these documents provide a comprehensive picture of how individual machine behaviors, shared spatial understanding, and operator interfaces are progressively integrated into a fully autonomous, multi-machine mining system.

3 Technical Details

3.1 Methodology

3.1.1 Autonomous Navigation of the Deployer Machine to an Operator-Specified Mine Face

As part of the initial integration efforts under Task 4.2, a primary objective has been to enable the Deployer machine to autonomously navigate to a specific mine face of interest, as selected by a human operator. This capability represents a fundamental link between exploratory mapping operations conducted by the *Explorer machine* (under Task 4.1) and subsequent mission-specific actions like drilling, excavation, or resource sampling.

The key assumption in this task is that the Deployer does not perform exploration on its own but instead relies on the spatial awareness constructed by the Explorer. This includes access to both:

- A dense voxel-based 3D map of the mine (represented using Voxelbox), and
- A global topological graph that encodes traversable pathways through the explored space.

These data products are transmitted to the Deployer machine, which can then use them to perform mission planning and safe navigation through the mine environment.

Machines Terminology:

- Explorer --> Machine 1 that autonomously explores and maps the unknown environment.
- Deployer --> Machine 2 that oversees autonomously navigating to area of interest (mine face) based on received information from Explorer machine.
- Supplier --> Machine 3 that brings reinforcements and additional robots such as the stinger robot to the mine face ahead of the deployment.

Operator-Guided Goal Specification:

The selection of the target mine face is performed manually by a human operator using a custom RViz2 GUI plugin, developed as part of this task. This interface allows the operator to inspect the shared 3D voxel map and to place a 3D waypoint directly within the visualized environment. This is critical in realistic mine settings, where mission-critical targets (e.g., drilling points or ore deposits) may be visually confirmed but not programmatically defined.

Once the waypoint is confirmed, the system triggers the “Navigate to Waypoint” behavior within the Deployer’s autonomy stack. This behavior is part of a broader hierarchical control structure, implemented using a behavior tree architecture, as illustrated in Figure 1. The structure allows flexible and modular task execution,

including localization verification, path planning, navigation execution, and fallbacks in case of failure.

Figure 1: STAGE Autonomy Behavior tree architecture used on the Deployer machine to manage autonomous operations. The “Navigate to Waypoint” behavior is triggered when a 3D goal is specified in RViz2. The behavior tree ensures modular and reactive execution of subtasks, including planning, control, and safety checks.

Shared Map Infrastructure and Planning:

As shown in Figure 2, the voxel map generated by the Explorer is a high-resolution 3D representation of the mine’s geometry, constructed using onboard LiDAR and real-time volumetric integration (Voxblox). This map, when sent to the Deployer, enables accurate localization, obstacle awareness, and path planning, even in the absence of external infrastructure such as GNSS or wifi beacons.

When a navigation request is triggered, the Deployer uses the shared global graph to compute an optimal path from its current location to the goal waypoint. This is performed using classical Dijkstra planning over the global graph, ensuring that the selected route adheres to known-safe paths. Because the map was built by a similar platform and sensor suite, the traversability assumptions made during exploration also apply to the Deployer.

In execution, the robot continuously monitors its position within the map, validating its trajectory against the known traversable corridors, and making local corrections when required. The planner also allows for segment-level re-planning if unexpected dynamic obstacles are encountered, although the primary focus here is to validate the full route-to-goal capability using pre-built maps.

This subtask is foundational to the broader goal of Task 4.2 establishing a machine that can transition from exploratory intelligence to precise, action-oriented autonomy. The approach not only demonstrates machine-to-machine map sharing but also highlights the use of operator-in-the-loop interaction to bridge high-level goals with on-board autonomous behavior.

Figure 2: Voxel-based 3D voxel map generated by the Explorer machine and shared with the Deployer. This map enables full-environment awareness for autonomous navigation, supporting planning through previously explored regions even in GPS-denied, unstructured settings.

3.1.2 Graph-Based Multi-Robot Mission Control via the *stage_gui_plugin*

To support flexible testing, rapid iteration, and scalable autonomy in both simulation and field deployments, we developed a custom control interface plugin: the *stage_gui_plugin*. This RViz2-integrated GUI tool plays a central role in the operation of autonomous machines under Tasks 4.1 and 4.2, and particularly in the coordination between the *Explorer* and *Deployer* platforms.

The plugin was designed with a modular architecture to support multi-machine autonomy, intuitive operator interaction, and dynamic mission configuration. It provides operators and researchers with an efficient and high-level interface to manage robot behavior without modifying internal autonomy pipelines or service-level implementations.

Figure 3: Screenshot of the *stage_gui_plugin*, an RViz2-integrated graphical interface for controlling autonomous machines in the STAGE system. The interface allows operators to select a robot, set mission timing, switch between exploration and waypoint-following behaviors, and manage voxel maps and navigation graphs. It also includes controls for pausing, launching, or returning from missions in both simulation and real-world scenarios.

Core Functionalities:

The GUI offers a wide range of configurable and runtime features:

- **Multi-Robot Selection:**The operator can select from a list of registered robots (e.g., *Explorer*, *Deployer*, or simulation instances like *husky*) at runtime. This allows for easy switching between machines with shared autonomy stacks, facilitating both single-robot and multi-agent coordination testing.
- **Mission Timing & Lifecycle Control:** Operators can define mission durations, initialize system states, and issue mission-critical commands such as *Takeoff*, *Land*, *Start Mission*, and *Return Home*. These features are essential for real-world field deployment and controlled evaluation in long-term trials.
- **Mapping and Graph Management:** One of the most powerful capabilities of the plugin is its ability to save and load voxel maps and navigation graphs. These operations allow an operator to persist the explored environment of

- one machine (typically the *Explorer*) and later share it with another (the *Deployer*). The GUI exposes buttons for:
- Save Map, Load Map: storing and restoring voxel map representations (e.g., from Voxblox).
 - Build Graph: constructs the global graph from the current local sub-graphs.
 - Save Graph, Load Graph: enables graph export/import to facilitate machine-to-machine sharing or post-processing.
 - Behavior Switching: The operator can dynamically switch between two key behaviors:
 - Explore: enables autonomous frontier-based exploration (as used by the Explorer).
 - Go to WP: activates the waypoint navigation behavior, typically used by the Deployer once a target has been specified.
 - Execution State Control: A lower-level toggle allows the operator to pause or resume the machine's actions. For example:
 - HOLD: immediately halts the robot (e.g., for safety or analysis).
 - PATH: resumes execution of the planned route.

Importance and Benefits:

This GUI significantly simplifies the complexity of interacting with a distributed autonomous system in challenging environments like underground mines. Without such a tool, researchers and field operators would have to issue ROS 2 service calls or manipulate configuration files manually a time-consuming and error-prone process.

By centralizing mission control in a visual interface:

- Operator-in-the-loop planning becomes intuitive, allowing goals to be defined visually and systems to be monitored in real time.
- Machine coordination is simplified, since graphs and maps can be transferred between robots without external infrastructure or scripting.
- Debugging and testing are accelerated, particularly when evaluating new autonomy modules, planner updates, or perception stacks.
- The plugin is also hardware-agnostic, supporting both aerial and ground platforms if they adhere to the same STAGE autonomy stack.

Overall, the `stage_gui_plugin` acts as both an operator console and a research instrument bridging the gap between low-level autonomy implementation and high-level task execution. It allows developers and field personnel to deploy, coordinate, and validate complex autonomous behavior across heterogeneous machines with minimal effort.

3.1.3 Demonstration Setup for Operator-Specified Waypoint Navigation in Shared Map Context

To validate the capability of the Deployer machine to navigate to an operator-defined mine face, a controlled simulation scenario was constructed in which the Deployer receives a voxel map and global graph from the Explorer machine. The map represents a previously explored section of the underground mine and is used by the Deployer for route planning and environment awareness. In this setup, we demonstrate the end-to-end autonomy pipeline: from operator interaction in the GUI, to waypoint planning, and autonomous motion execution by the Deployer.

Figure 4: Simulation setup for operator-specified waypoint navigation by the Deployer machine. The map shown is provided by the Explorer machine. The Deployer uses a 6-DOF interactive marker (center inset) to set a goal location on the mine face. Since the simulation environment shares a global reference frame, no re-localization is required, and the planner can directly compute a path from the Deployer's starting location to the target area.

As illustrated in Figure 4, the environment visualized belongs to the *Deployer's perspective*, but it is based entirely on map data generated by the *Explorer*. The starting location of the Deployer machine is shown on the left side of the map, while an operator-specified area of interest (in this case, a mine face) is located on the far right. The operator interacts with the system through a custom-developed RViz2 interface, placing a 6-degree-of-freedom (6-DOF) interactive marker on the voxel map to define both the position and orientation of the desired goal.

The goal definition process is intuitive and visual: the operator simply clicks and aligns the marker to set the desired pose for the Deployer machine. Once this input is confirmed, the *stage_gui_plugin* transitions the system into “Navigate to Waypoint” mode. The Deployer then computes a global path from its current position to the defined goal using the global graph structure received from the Explorer machine.

3.1.3.1 Simulation-Specific Considerations

A key benefit in this simulation demonstration is that both the Explorer and Deployer machines operate within the same simulated world frame. This means the voxel map and global graph created by the Explorer are already perfectly aligned with the Deployer's coordinate system. As a result, there is no need for inter-robot re-localization a challenge that would arise in real-world deployments where each robot operates with its own internal localization estimate.

This simplification is intentional at this stage, as the current focus is on validating the path planning and navigation logic. Future work on re-localization across machines will be addressed under Work Package 5, Task 5.2, where we will explore cross-robot map registration and localization correction strategies to support map sharing under real-world uncertainties.

This demonstration proves that the system can handle:

- Dynamic operator interaction for goal assignment.
- Graph-based long-distance planning from any valid start to target point.
- Consistent map and graph utilization across two autonomous machines.

It provides a strong foundation for the upcoming integration of real-world sensing, localization drift handling, and full autonomy in degraded conditions.

Figure 5: Global path planning from the Deployer's starting location to an operator-specified mine face. The path is computed using the global graph generated by the Explorer machine. The operator sets a goal near the mine face, and the Deployer autonomously plans and prepares to follow a collision-free global route through the previously explored map.

3.1.4 Global Path Planning to Operator-Specified Mine Face Using Shared Graph

Following the operator's specification of a goal location near the mine face using the interactive marker interface (previously shown in Figure 4), the Deployer machine successfully generated a global plan to reach the mine face, as visualized in Figure 5. This demonstration illustrates the integration of core components developed under Tasks 4.1 and 4.2: shared spatial representation, goal setting, and autonomous global path planning.

In this scenario, the map and graph were constructed by the Explorer machine during its prior exploration of the environment. This data was then transmitted to the Deployer machine, which initialized with the same spatial representation of the mine. The voxel map provided environmental geometry for obstacle-aware planning, while the global graph encoded traversable connections between known locations, including corridors, junctions, and explored branches.

Once the operator defined the 6-DOF waypoint near the desired mine face, the Deployer entered waypoint navigation mode. It began by identifying its current position within the graph (starting location at the bottom left of the figure) and used Dijkstra's algorithm to plan an optimal path to the mine face. This path is highlighted in Figure 5 as the planned global route spanning the full length of the mine corridor.

This example validates the following key aspects of our approach:

- Machine-to-machine handoff: The Deployer was able to operate entirely based on map and graph data it did not collect itself.
- Operator-driven autonomy: The human operator was able to define a meaningful goal visually, without needing to manually input coordinates or waypoints.
- Scalable graph-based planning: The system planned over a large, complex environment using graph-based search, providing fast and reliable navigation paths.

Figure 6 : Multiple navigation tasks executed by the Deployer machine in the simulated GM mine. In each case, the operator selected different mine faces as waypoints. The Deployer planned and followed the global route autonomously using the previously shared map and graph, demonstrating the robustness of the navigation pipeline in varied spatial conditions.

The final waypoint lies in the proximity of a mine face previously explored and mapped by the Explorer. Once the Deployer reaches this target, future work will focus on fine alignment for drilling preparation and evaluating spatial constraints for machine positioning, as required by downstream drilling operations.

This demonstration confirms that the STAGE planning architecture along with the RViz2 goal interface and shared global graph supports reliable, infrastructure-free navigation in large-scale subterranean environments with minimal operator effort.

In Figure 6, we present additional instances of the Deployer machine autonomously navigating to multiple operator-specified mine faces within the

simulated Grecian Magnesite (GM) mine environment. Each panel depicts a different goal location set using the 6-DOF marker in RViz2 and the corresponding traversal route computed and executed by the Deployer using the shared global graph and voxel map previously generated by the Explorer machine.

These additional trials showcase the resiliency and repeatability of the STAGE planning system: regardless of where the goal is placed, the Deployer can identify a valid path and navigate entirely autonomously across complex tunnel networks. Even in regions with dense topology and highly branched corridors, the system demonstrates consistent behavior, proving that the combination of operator-defined flexibility and robust back-end planning enables flexible deployment of autonomous machines in large, partially known underground spaces.

These results reinforce the system's capability to function as a drop-in navigation module that can respond to high-level operator intentions with fully autonomous execution, an essential requirement for future real-world deployment in variable mine layouts.

3.1.5 Novel VLM-based segmentation of the mine face to accurately localize the magnesite ore concentration.

Semantic segmentation is the task of assigning a class label to each pixel in an image, such that all pixels corresponding to the same semantic category (e.g., road, person, tree) receive the same label. The objective is to produce a dense, pixel-level classification that partitions the image into semantically meaningful regions. This task differs from image classification and object detection by requiring a comprehensive understanding of the spatial structure and context within the image. Semantic segmentation is essential for applications where detailed scene understanding is critical, such as autonomous navigation, medical image analysis, and robotic perception. It serves as a foundational component in systems that must interpret complex visual environments at a fine-grained level.

However, semantic segmentation in perceptually degraded environments such as those with poor lighting, motion blur, fog, or occlusions poses unique challenges. In such conditions, conventional models often struggle due to reduced feature visibility and generalization issues. VLMs help mitigate some of these limitations by grounding segmentation not purely on low-level visual features but also on high-level semantic concepts encoded through text. This language-guided segmentation provides an additional inductive bias that can support more robust identification of objects, even when visual cues are partially degraded.

The choice of a vision-language model (VLM) offers several advantages over traditional segmentation approaches. First, VLMs enable prompt-driven inference, allowing flexible, zero-shot or few-shot segmentation without requiring retraining or extensive labeled datasets for each specific class of interest. This flexibility is particularly beneficial in robotics, where tasks and environments can change dynamically and where deploying retrained models for each new scenario is impractical.

To perform semantic segmentation, the CLIPSeg model was employed, a transformer-based model trained on paired image-text data, leveraging its capability to segment images based on natural language prompts. CLIPSeg was chosen specifically due to its lightweight architecture and its effectiveness in performing prompt-based segmentation without needing class-specific training. Compared to other VLM-based segmentation models, CLIPSeg strikes a balance between accuracy, speed, and computational efficiency, making it well-suited for real-time perception tasks in robotic systems operating under uncertainty and variability.

Figure 7: Zero-shot semantic segmentation based on CLIPSeg.

The process was designed to be modular and efficient, enabling integration into robotic perception systems. CLIPSeg was loaded using pre-trained weights. This model accepts an RGB image and a text prompt and outputs a segmentation mask highlighting regions in the image corresponding to the prompt. This allowed segmentation of semantically relevant regions based on human-interpretable descriptions (e.g., "white mineral"). The pipeline can handle a live video stream or a static dataset. The steps for processing each image were as follows:

1. Input Acquisition and Preparation:

- A set of natural language prompts is entered (e.g., "white mineral"), separated by commas.
- The selected image is read using OpenCV and converted from BGR (OpenCV default) to RGB format for compatibility with the CLIPSeg model.

2. Prompt and Image Preprocessing

- For each prompt, the CLIPSeg processor prepares the image and text inputs:
 - The image is resized and normalized to match the model's expected input format.
 - The text prompts are tokenized and transformed into embeddings that can be interpreted by the transformer model.
 - Each prompt-image pair is stacked into a batch (one for each prompt), allowing parallel processing of multiple semantic concepts.

3. Model Inference

- The pre-trained CLIPSeg model (CIDAS/clipseg-rd64-refined) performs inference on the batch of inputs.
- The model outputs a set of *logit maps*, where each map corresponds to the predicted relevance of pixels to a specific prompt.
- A sigmoid activation is applied to convert logits to probabilities, producing soft masks that represent per-pixel likelihoods.

4. Multi-Prompt Fusion

- If multiple prompts are used, the corresponding soft masks are *combined multiplicatively* (i.e., via element-wise product). This ensures that only regions satisfying all prompt conditions are emphasized, which can be useful for refining specificity (e.g., "white mineral" AND "glowing").
- If a single prompt is used, its mask is directly used as the prediction.

5. Postprocessing and Visualization

- The resulting soft mask is resized back to the original image dimensions.
- A colormap (e.g., *magma*) is applied to the soft mask to create a visually interpretable heatmap.
- This heatmap is then overlaid onto the original image using alpha blending, creating a composite that visually highlights the segmented regions.
- The name of the prompt(s) is annotated onto the image for clarity.

Figure 8: Comparison of Magnesite Segmentation on Image Frames

Figure 9: A Visual Language Model based approach towards autonomous Magnesite Segmentation on the Video Feed.

In applications involving spatial reasoning, the 2D segmentation mask will be used to filter depth or point cloud data. For each segmented region:

- Corresponding 3D points will be extracted using camera intrinsics.
- Global bounding boxes will be computed to localize segmented objects in the environment.
- These results will be published for downstream tasks such as navigation, object tracking, or scene understanding.

CLIPSeg was chosen for its ability to generalize to unseen classes using zero-shot learning. This eliminated the need for class-specific training and allowed rapid adaptation to new environments and tasks. To maintain real-time performance:

- Inference was accelerated using GPU hardware.
- Batching and asynchronous processing techniques were employed when handling continuous image streams.

3.1.6 Precise navigation to the mine face considering the size and operational constraints of machines

In underground environments, precise positioning of autonomous platforms near the mine face is essential for enabling safe and effective execution of downstream tasks such as high-resolution mapping, material deployment, or sensor-based inspection. To this end, we have developed a dedicated perception and control module that enables the deployer robot to autonomously approach the mine face and align itself for continued operation, considering the spatial constraints of the tunnel and the robot's footprint.

Once the STAGE autonomy pipeline brings the robot to a location near the operator-specified region of interest typically the approximate mine face the final alignment step ensures the robot is not only in the right vicinity but also properly oriented relative to the face surface. This alignment is critical for guaranteeing that forward-facing sensors or deployable tools maintain optimal orientation for data acquisition or actuation.

To compute the correct alignment, the system processes incoming LiDAR point clouds to extract the dominant planar surface in front of the robot. This is achieved by estimating surface normals across the point cloud, followed by RANSAC-based plane fitting to detect the structural geometry of the tunnel face. From the resulting plane, the normal vector is computed and used to derive a target heading that ensures the robot is oriented perpendicularly to the surface.

This computed orientation vector visualized as a red arrow in the accompanying figures represents the ideal heading direction. The robot then calculates a safe standoff distance from the plane and generates a final navigation goal that places it directly in front of the mine face while ensuring sufficient maneuvering clearance.

Figure 10 : Point cloud visualizations from LiDAR data showing the final alignment process near the mine face. The red panels represent detected planar surfaces corresponding to the tunnel wall or mine face, while the b indicates the computed alignment vector the direction the robot should be facing for optimal approach and interaction. Each image shows a distinct instance where the deployer robot successfully identifies the surface normal and determines a goal orientation for autonomous alignment.

This final step completes the approach sequence and guarantees that the deployer is well-positioned for high-precision operations, regardless of tunnel curvature or slope. Automating this orientation process eliminates the need for manual

alignment, significantly improving reliability and repeatability in confined underground deployments.

3.1.7 Evaluation of multi sensor setup to demonstrate undisturbed operation in visually degraded environments

Different sensors fail under different conditions. For example, LiDAR and RGB cameras degrade significantly in dusty or smoky environments due to scattering and absorption of light. Radar, on the other hand, is largely immune to these visual obstructions as it uses radio waves that penetrate dust, fog, and smoke. By fusing data from multiple sensors like LiDAR, radar, IMU, thermal, RGB cameras. The system can continue to operate reliably even if one or more sensors are compromised.

How radars help in such situations:

The rapid evolution of radar and LiDAR technologies, driven by advancements in the automotive and robotics industries, has significantly improved capabilities in localization, mapping, and 3D object detection, especially in environments where traditional sensors underperform. Both radar and LiDAR function as active sensing systems, identifying and characterizing targets by interpreting backscattered signals.

Figure 11: A schematic of the Multi-Radar Inertial Odometry (MRIO) framework, which integrates inputs from an IMU and multiple radars mounted on a mobile robot to obtain odometry, including localization, ego velocity, and a radar point-cloud map.

In underground environments such as tunnels and subterranean facilities, the lack of GPS signals and reduced visibility due to darkness, dense smoke, and airborne particles can severely compromise the effectiveness of LiDAR and vision-based systems. Numerous studies have shown that LiDAR performance degrades under adverse weather conditions, including heavy smoke, fog, rain, and snow, which challenges its reliability in real-world applications. To address these shortcomings, radar technology has emerged as a strong alternative, owing to its robustness in extreme environments. Radar sensors maintain consistent measurements in low-visibility and harsh weather conditions, ensuring reliable perception and navigation. As a result, radar is increasingly recognized as a dependable solution for operations in challenging settings. However, radar point clouds tend to be sparse, noisy, and cluttered, with data typically available only

when there is relative movement between the sensor and its surroundings. Multipath reflections and dynamic elements like pedestrian motion often introduce outliers, leading to potential drift in radar-based ego-velocity estimation and relative positioning, influenced by factors such as environmental dynamics. Additionally, reflections from surfaces like floors and walls can distort point clouds and Doppler measurements. Nevertheless, recent advancements in radar perception have significantly improved performance in ego-motion estimation, localization, dynamic object tracking, and environmental mapping.

Evaluation of radars in no smoke environments:

The capability to perceive and navigate effectively in smoke-filled environments is vital for numerous applications, such as search and rescue missions, autonomous robotics, and industrial safety. Conventional sensors like cameras and LiDAR often struggle in these conditions, as smoke particles scatter and absorb light, leading to reduced performance. In contrast, radar sensors, which rely on radio waves, are more resilient to visual obstructions and present a promising alternative. This project aims to evaluate radar effectiveness in smoke-dense settings by examining their ability to detect objects, localize, and generate maps reliably. Through experimental studies and analysis, the goal is to assess radar's robustness, identify challenges such as noise and multipath interference, and investigate methods to improve radar-based perception in low-visibility environments. The experimental data were gathered using the Pioneer 3-AT2 platform in an underground setting located in Luleå, Sweden. The trials specifically took place in a junction area that begins with a narrow tunnel approximately 3.5 meters wide and gradually opens up to a width of around 10 meters, as depicted in the figure below:

(a) **Environment-1:** Experimental environment without smoke

(b) **Environment-2:** Experimental environment in presence of smoke

Figure 12: Representative experimental environment inside Sub-T tunnel with and without smoke. Map of the experimental area is shown in the upper left corner of each image, was generated from the 3D LiDAR measurements.

The vehicle was operated in the tunnel under two distinct environmental conditions. The first condition, referred to as Environment 1, is illustrated in Figure 12(a), while the second condition, labeled Environment 2, is shown in Figure 12(b). Throughout the experiments, four different radar configurations

were evaluated across various scenarios. Specifically, Configuration-1 employs a single front-facing radar (R-2), Configuration 2 utilizes two radars (R-2 and R-3), Configuration 3 incorporates four radars (R-1, R-2, R-3, and R-4), and Configuration 4 involves all six radars (R-1, R-2, R-3, R-4, R-5, and R-6). These configurations are illustrated in Figure 13. A comprehensive summary of the experiments conducted in the subterranean tunnel with no smoke is provided in Tables (1) and (2).

Table 1: Descriptions of robot navigation Environment 1(a)- 1(d)

Environment	Path Type	Smoke Condition	Radar Configuration
1(a)	Straight line	Smoke-free	Single radar, R2
1(b)	Straight line	Smoke-free	2 radars, R2, R3
1(c)	Straight line	Smoke-free	4 radars, R1,, R4
1(d)	Straight line	Smoke-free	6 radars R1,...., R6

Table 2: Descriptions of robot navigation Environment 1(e)- 1(h)

Environment	Path Type	Smoke Condition	Radar Configuration
1(e)	L-shaped	Smoke free	Single radar, R2
1(f)	L-shaped	Smoke free	2 radars, R2, R3
1(g)	L-shaped	Smoke free	4 radars R1,....,R4
1(h)	L-shaped	Smoke free	6 radars, R1,.....R6

During the experimental phase, as the robot moved through the tunnel, the radar sensor suite continuously collected data, capturing radar target points along with their corresponding Doppler velocities under various test conditions, thereby supporting the successful achievement of the experiment’s objectives.

Figure 13 : The schematic illustrates the sensor layout featuring six FMCW radars and an IMU. The left panel presents a top-down view, while the right panel shows the side view of the setup. The IMU is mounted near the center of the platform. The system includes six mm-wave Texas Instruments IWR6843AoP ES2.0 radars (Radar-1 to Radar-6), arranged as follows: Radars 1 through 4 are evenly spaced at 90° intervals around the sides of the

robot, ensuring full environmental coverage. Radars 5 and 6 are mounted at the front and rear of the platform, each angled upward at 45° to monitor the ceiling from both directions.

Because radar sensors rely on detecting relative motion, they do not produce measurements when the robot is stationary. Once the robot starts moving during the experiments, the radar system captures raw target reflections known as radar point clouds from surfaces such as the walls, floor, and ceiling, along with Doppler velocity data generated by relative movement. The experimental results showed that mmWave radar reflections are sometimes caused by small airborne particles like dust, leading to 'ghost targets' or false detections, which introduce inaccuracies in the point cloud. Furthermore, due to multipath effects, clusters of reflected points often appear around the robot itself.

Considering this, the following section provides more detail. The process begins with a range-based outlier rejection method, using sensing limits of $R_o=6$ meters and $R_I=1$ meter across all radar configurations. This technique is applied to each time-stamped radar scan to effectively eliminate outlier measurements as shown in the figures. Once the unwanted data is filtered out, the remaining radar pointclouds are combined into a single representation per time instance, referred to as the merged pointclouds. This merging process includes the necessary frame transformations converting the individual radar measurements into the robot's body frame.

Figure 14 : Evaluation of localization and mapping performance in a smoke-free setting as the robot moves along a nearly straight path. The visualizations include the radar-based point cloud map (dark blue), MRIO-based

trajectory (red line), and LiDAR-based trajectory (black line), all overlaid on the 3D LiDAR map (multi-coloured dotted points). Each subplot corresponds to a different radar configuration.

The experimental evaluation in the Environment-1, considers smoke-free condition with a low visibility scenario, where the robot navigates through a near straight line as well as an 'L'-Shaped trajectories, as illustrated in Figure 15(a) and 15(b). Note that the outcome of the MRIO framework, providing radar inertial odometry, consists of estimated robot position, velocity, and orientation. Experimental results illustrating the localization and mapping presented in Figures 14, 16, 17, 18 demonstrate the performance of the proposed MRIO framework in Figure 11, evaluated in smoke-free conditions.

(a) Navigating along an 'L' shaped trajectory in environment without smoke

(b) Navigating along a near straight trajectory in environment without smoke

Figure 15: Experiment:1, A low-light subterranean environment without the presence of smoke. The experimental scenarios illustrated include on the left, the robot moves along an 'L'-shaped path, turning at the junction; on the right, it travels along a nearly straight trajectory. The starting positions are marked at the forefront of each image

Using the estimated position and orientation of the ground robot, the aggregated radar point clouds from each scan are transformed into the global frame, enabling the generation of radar-based point cloud maps, as shown in Figures (14), (17). These maps illustrate the surrounding environment from a top-down X-Y plane perspective as the robot operates under different radar configurations. The figures display maps created with radar point clouds (shown as dark blue dots) using the proposed MRIO framework, alongside 3D LiDAR maps (represented by multi-colored dots) produced via the Direct LiDAR Odometry (DLO) method.

(a) MRIO Performance with measurement from radar mounted on the front

(b) MRIO Performance with measurement from two radars (front and back)

(c) MRIO Performance with four radars (front, back, left, right) measurements

(d) MRIO Performance with measurement from all six radars configuration

Figure 16 : Localization performance assessment using the MRIO framework in a smoke-free scenario, where the robot follows a nearly straight path. The red line represents the robot's X-Y trajectory estimated by MRIO, while the black line shows the trajectory derived from the LIO method.

Importantly, the spatial accuracy and structure of the map produced by the proposed MRIO framework closely resemble those generated by the LIO-based method, demonstrating the effectiveness of the MRIO approach. Additionally, the quality of the radar-based map improves with the use of more radars in multi-radar configurations, as a greater number of point clouds are registered during each scan. Nonetheless, as expected, in smoke-free conditions (Environment-1), LiDAR provides more precise mapping of the surroundings compared to radar. The robot trajectories derived from odometry are overlaid on the maps. To further illustrate localization performance, these trajectories are also shown separately in Figures 16,18.

The results confirm that in Environment-1, the robot moved along an almost straight path, whereas in Environment-2, it followed a smooth L-shaped route. At each time step, scans from multiple radars are combined to estimate the robot's ego-velocity using a least squares method. The variations in these estimated ego-velocities across different scenarios are illustrated with green solid lines in the Figure 20.

Figure 17 : Environment 1(a)-(d): Performance evaluation of localization and mapping in a low-visibility, smoke-free scenario while the robot navigates along a 'L' shaped trajectory. Representing the Radar based point-clouds map (thick dotted deep blue point-clouds), MRIO based localization (red solid line), overlaid on the 3D-LiDAR map (thin dotted multi-colored point-clouds) and LiDAR-based localization (black solid line).

In the first-layer EKF (Stage-I), ego-velocity measurements are fused with IMU acceleration data, and the resulting estimated ego-velocity profiles are shown as blue solid lines. This fusion enhances the reliability of the ego-velocity estimation. Since the environment is free of smoke, the LiDAR sensor performs optimally, providing a highly accurate reference. Given the reliability of LIO in such conditions, it is used as a benchmark for comparison. To achieve this, the LIO-based position data is numerically differentiated over time to derive the corresponding velocity, represented by black dashed lines. The results clearly show that radar-based ego-velocity estimates closely match the LiDAR based velocities across all test scenarios. Furthermore, the fusion approach offers a more robust velocity estimate than relying solely on the least squares method.

Figure 18: Performance evaluation of trajectory estimation using MRIO in the smoke-free scenario as the robot navigates through a 'L' shaped path. The red line indicates the (X-Y) trajectory of the ground robot obtained from the proposed MRIO framework, where the black line denotes the trajectory obtained based on LIO

An important observation is that, despite the highly encouraging ego-velocity estimates (Fig-20) produced by the first-stage EKF across all scenarios, our initial attempt to use this same EKF for localization failed. The resulting trajectory showed significant drift and was far from accurate, as illustrated in Figure 19, prompting a deeper analysis of key intermediate steps.

Figure 19 : Intermediate results illustrating the X-Y trajectory analysis from experimental data as the robot navigates an 'L'-shaped path in a smoke-free setting. (a) Trajectory derived from direct integration of the estimated ego-velocity, showing substantial drift due to the effects of dead reckoning. (b) Trajectory estimated

using the Stage-I EKF, which also exhibits significant drift, primarily because RIO lacks direct position updates and the bias in acceleration measurements remains uncorrected.

To investigate further, we began by numerically integrating the ego-velocity profile to estimate the robot's trajectory, as shown in Figure: 19 (b). As expected, this direct integration approach suffered from the classic dead reckoning issue, with drift appearing early on. In contrast, the trajectory estimated using the first-stage EKF followed a recognizable 'L'-shaped path depicted by a faded marigold-colored solid line in Figure: 19(a). However, it still showed increasing deviation over time. These findings led us to re-examine the acceleration data from the IMU.

Figure 20 : Performance evaluation of ego-velocity estimation in a low-visibility, smoke-free scenario as the robot navigates an 'L'-shaped path. The least square based velocity estimates are denoted with green, MRIO-based ego-velocity estimation is represented by blue solid lines, while the 3D-LiDAR-based velocity is depicted by black. In a smoke-free scenario, MRIO-based velocity estimation closely matches with velocity from the LiDARs

IMU offset calibration: All experiments were carried out in an underground tunnel environment, where the ambient temperature was extremely low around -20°C . Under these conditions, the IMU measurements were affected by thermal drift, leading to residual offsets in the acceleration data. Such thermal-induced drift in IMU readings is a well-known issue, as documented in studies evaluating IMU performance across temperature ranges from $+45^{\circ}\text{C}$ to -10°C . These residual

offsets have a notable impact on the accuracy of odometry. To mitigate this problem, this work introduces an additional correction mechanism aimed at producing an offset-free estimate of forward acceleration.

Figure 21 : Acceleration offset correction results across different radar configurations, compared against raw IMU acceleration data, for a near straight-line trajectory in a smoke-free setting. The filtered forward acceleration, depicted by blue solid lines, effectively removes dynamic offsets using the MRIO framework, while the uncorrected IMU acceleration is shown as green dashed lines.

The raw IMU measurements, illustrated in the Figure 21, with green solid lines, exhibit noise and residual offsets. As a result, directly using these measurements for odometry makes the system highly prone to drift accumulation, leading to growing localization errors that remain uncorrected, as demonstrated in the Figure 18. To overcome this, a two-stage fusion strategy is essential for achieving accurate odometry, especially in loosely coupled estimation scenarios. This method introduces a second layer of error correction, where corrected, offset-free IMU acceleration is used for additional filtering, significantly enhancing odometry accuracy.

The estimation of residual offsets is handled in Stage I, as shown in Figure 21, by integrating velocity estimates from the first-stage EKF, the proposed velocity-

augmented acceleration correction method effectively reduces measurement noise and compensates for residual offsets in the forward acceleration, as demonstrated in the figures where the resulting smooth, offset-free acceleration profiles are depicted by blue solid lines. To assess the accuracy of the estimated forward acceleration, a comparison is made with more reliable LiDAR-based data under smoke-free conditions. In this comparison, the LIO derived position estimates are numerically differentiated to approximate the acceleration. It is important to emphasize that the proposed framework operates entirely independently of LiDAR, LiDAR-based results are used solely for validation and comparison across all scenarios discussed in this deliverable.

(a) The estimated acceleration (blue) is compared with the acceleration derived from LiDAR measurements (black) (b) Estimated dynamic offset between the raw IMU acceleration and the acceleration obtained from the Stage-I filter

Figure 22 : Comparison of acceleration estimates from MRIO and LIO. The acceleration offset is determined by contrasting the raw IMU data with the MRIO-derived estimates, as the robot follows a nearly straight trajectory.

The estimated residual acceleration offsets are shown in Figure:22(b). These offset profiles indicate that the raw acceleration data is affected by both measurement noise and dynamic drift. During the primary operation period, the offsets reach magnitudes of approximately 0.5 m/s², resulting in a noticeable non-zero mean in both experimental scenarios. Additionally, close inspection reveals that these residual offsets are not constant over time and vary between experiments. This highlights that raw IMU acceleration data, significantly influenced by noise and dynamic bias, is unsuitable for accurate odometry if used directly. The robot's orientation, specifically the heading angle, is estimated in Stage-II using IMU data. The variation in heading angles across different scenarios is shown in Figs.:23, 24.

(a) Single Radar configuration

(b) Two Radars configurations

(c) Four Radars configuration

(d) Six Radars configuration

Figure 23: Orientation estimation while navigation along the near straight path

The orientation estimates produced by the MRIO framework closely align with those obtained from LIO. Since MRIO relies solely on IMU data for orientation and is independent of radar input, it consistently yields the same orientation estimates regardless of the radar configuration, as illustrated in Figures 23 and 24. This consistency is observed across all experimental environments.

(e) Single Radar configuration

(f) Two Radars configurations

(g) Four Radars configuration

(h) Six Radars configuration

Figure 24: Orientation estimation while navigation along the near 'L' shaped path.

Evaluation of radars in smoke filled environments:

The experimental Environment-2, depicted in Figure 12(b), is characterised by a subterranean tunnel with spread-out dense smoke, high humidity, and darkness, making it challenging for sensors like cameras and LiDAR to function effectively. This experiment aims to evaluate the performance of radars in such harsh conditions, where most of the sensors often fail to provide accurate measurements. The following experimental results illustrate the performance of MRIO-based odometry, while the robot is navigating along the nearly identical 'L'-shape path, as the navigation environment in the Table. 3,

Table 3: Descriptions of robot navigation Environment 2(a) - 1(d)

Environment	Path Type	Smoke Condition	Radar Configuration
2(a)	L-shaped	Smoke-filled	Single radar, R_2
2(b)	L-shaped	Smoke-filled	2 radars, R_2, R_3
2(c)	L-shaped	Smoke-filled	4 radars, R_1, \dots, R_4
2(d)	L-shaped	Smoke-filled	6 radars, R_1, \dots, R_6

Figure 25 presents the radar and LiDAR point-cloud-based maps. Collaborative radar point clouds, represented by deep blue dots, form the maps generated by the proposed MRIO framework in the presence of smoke. Additionally, the MRIO-

based estimated position of the robot during navigation is indicated with red solid lines. The corresponding estimated trajectories, without the maps, are individually shown in Figure 26

Figure 25: MRIO and the corresponding map generated with different numbers of radars mounted on the robot, in a smoke-filled environment. The red solid line and deep blue point clouds indicate the RIO and the map, while the multi-coloured map and the black line represent the 3D LiDAR-based map and its localization, respectively.

Performance with different radar configurations is highlighted in the corresponding subplots. As the number of radars increases, the robot's perception improves, capturing radar target points from all directions and constructing a more detailed and representative map of the environment. Additionally, with an increasing number of radars, the localisation accuracy also improves. It is evident that the maps obtained in Figure 25, representatively, reflect the 'L' shape pattern, equivalent to the environment highlighted in Figure 15, corroborating the expected experimental outcome as the robot navigates. In contrast, the LiDAR point-cloud based map is presented with multi-colour dots, following the similar representation depicted in Figure 17

The overlaid black dashed lines represent the LIO-based position estimation of the ground robot. Note that both experiments, with and without smoke, are conducted in the same part of the tunnel. Comparing the figures in Figure 17 and Figure 25, it is evident that in the presence of smoke, the LiDAR point-cloud density is extremely less. Moreover, generated LiDAR-based maps are not representative and fail to even capture the 'L' shape tunnel and associated trajectory.

(a) Validate the accuracy of our proposed framework for single radar configuration

(b) Highlighting the trajectory for two radars comparison when LiDAR fails to deliver results

(c) The localization performance for configurations with four radars in dense smoke

(d) Trajectory comparison between six-radar configuration in the MRIO framework and LiDAR

Figure 26: Performance evaluation of trajectory estimation using the proposed MRIO in the presence of dense smoke as the robot navigates an 'L' shaped path. The red line represents the (X-Y) trajectory of the ground robot obtained from our MRIO framework, while the black line shows the trajectory based on DLO. It is evident that the LiDAR failed to perceive due to the dense smoke and could not follow the 'L' shaped path.

The underground tunnel area where the experiment is performed, consists of multiple branches, but the smoke is introduced only along the L-shaped trajectory. As the robot navigates through the 'L'-shaped path, the smoke gradually obstructs the LiDAR perception system. Since smoke is not introduced in all the other branches of the tunnels, as the robot reaches the junction point, the LiDAR scan perceives and maps the unobstructed straight follow-up tunnel section beyond the junction, as depicted in Figure 12.

Notably, at this point, the LiDAR-based perception fails to recognise that the robot is navigating along a completely different trajectory. Instead, it quickly captures the unobstructed straight tunnel beyond the junction, entirely ignoring the smoke-filled 'L'-shaped path the robot was following. This misinterpretation leads to incorrect localization and map predictions, as shown in Figures 25 and 26.

Figure 27: Environment 2(a)-(d): Performance evaluation of Ego Velocity estimation using MRIO

The estimated ego velocity of the ground robot, based on MRIO and LIO, is presented in Figure 27. During the experiment, the robot navigated at nearly constant velocity, approximately of the order of 0.2 m/s. The variation in measured ego-velocities for different radar configurations is highlighted with blue solid lines. It can be observed that the LIO-based ego velocity exhibits significant fluctuations, with variations of approximately ± 4 m/s, which deviate substantially from the expected performance.

Variation of acceleration profiles is presented in Figure 29, the measured forward acceleration, obtained from raw measurement of IMU, is presented with a green solid line, while the MRIO-based estimated acceleration is shown with blue solid lines. The IMU acceleration is affected by measurement noise and residual offsets.

The estimated acceleration offset is shown in Figure 28, prominently reflecting that its mean follows a dynamic variation with time. Additionally, the figure provides insights into the variations and inconsistencies in the raw data, emphasising the importance of the offset calibration approach considered in the MRIO framework to obtain more accurate acceleration estimates.

For completeness, a comparison with the base acceleration estimate is presented in Figure 28, where it is evident that the LIO-based acceleration deviates significantly, with an unreliably high dispersion in acceleration magnitude.

Figure 28: A comparison of the estimated acceleration obtained from MRIO with LIO is presented. The acceleration offset is determined by comparing IMU measurements with the MRIO-based estimate as the robot navigates through a smoke-filled environment.

The variation of the orientations is presented in Figure 30. The orientation profiles obtained from MRIO largely deviate from the LIO-based orientation. It is apparent from the performance of all critical parameters for odometry that LiDAR-based estimates become unreliable when the robot enters the smoke-filled region. A critical observation to note here is that, in order to disperse the dense smoke and maintain its presence throughout the experiment, the individuals involved in spraying the smoke had to remain in the environment, and their movements were also captured by the radar as target points. Additionally, the smoke used in this experiment consisted of dense aerosol particles, which were detected by the radar as false target points. Despite these challenges, the proposed MRIO framework effectively estimated the odometry, demonstrating its robust performance.

Figure 29: Environment 2(a)-(d): Estimated acceleration from Stage I in the presence of dense smoke within the underground environment.

The experimental results provide valuable insights into the strengths and limitations of radar-based odometry and mapping. A key takeaway is that ego-velocity measurements serve as the primary input from radars, which form the foundation of the MRIO framework. While MRIO-based localisation performs effectively in the initial stages of navigation, closely aligning with LIO-based trajectories. This deviation arises due to the loosely coupled nature of the RIO framework, where radars lack direct position measurement for correction of the localisation error. This leads to the necessity for accurate acceleration measurement, more apparent when addressing the limitations of radar-based localisation. By employing a two-stage filtering approach, the MRIO framework refines pose estimation to achieve the best possible accuracy.

(a) Orientation estimation with single radar in a smoke-filled subterranean environment. (b) Orientation estimation with two radars in a smoke-filled subterranean environment

(c) Orientation estimation with four radars in a smoke-filled subterranean environment (d) Orientation estimation with six radars in a smoke-filled subterranean environment

Figure 30: Orientation estimation in the MRIO framework using multiple radar configurations in smoke-filled environments, compared with LiDAR.

Radar-based maps are one of the key contributions in scenarios particularly in environments with dense smoke, dust, or poor lighting. These maps are instrumental in operations like search-and-rescue missions, firefighting, and underground exploration. However, it is evident from the results that relying solely on radar for long-range exploration would not be a recommended practice. Instead, radar-based systems would perfectly fit to complement LiDAR in critical scenarios, acting as an additional support system in conditions where LiDAR struggles.

4 Partners Contributions:

Task 4.2 is led by the LTU team, who are responsible for extending the capabilities of the STAGE exploration planner to enable targeted navigation behavior. In particular, the robot is directed to autonomously navigate toward the mine face by leveraging the voxel map and exploration graph generated by a preceding exploratory machine. This enables coordinated multi-stage autonomy in a mining context. In addition, the Perception team at LTU contributes to Task 4.2 by developing a novel video-language model (VLM)-based segmentation approach for identifying magnesite cores directly from raw video streams. This capability supports vision-based decision-making in underground environments where explicit feature detection is crucial. To address the challenge of perception in degraded visual conditions, such as smoke-filled environments where LiDAR performance is limited, the LTU team also investigates the use of radar sensing. This extension enables evaluation of sensor fusion and multi-modal localization strategies to maintain accurate machine positioning under harsh environmental conditions. UPAT team contributed to this 4.2 development effort through assistance with debugging and planning best sensor placements and configuration of the SLAM system for detailed analysis in simulation. Discussions with EPI and MRP have also led in the direction of making a digital twin of the GM and KGHM mines through collected pointcloud scans.

5 Future Plans

The technical developments described in this deliverable will be further matured and validated in hardware as part of continuation activities in WP4 and WP5. Specifically:

- The autonomous navigation and alignment modules will be integrated onto physical robotic platforms for full system testing in subterranean environments, as part of Task 4.5.
- This testing will also involve close collaboration with DTU and UPAT partners, who are developing modules for drilling and ore handling, ensuring compatibility between perception, navigation, and manipulation systems.
- The radar-based odometry will be further evaluated under real environmental conditions to refine its use as a fallback or complementary localization source.
- These activities will culminate in integrated system demonstrations under WP5, particularly within Tasks 5.2 and 5.5, where multi-agent field trials will validate the autonomy stack in representative mining scenarios.

These future efforts will ensure that the technologies developed in Task 4.2 transition from simulation to robust field-ready autonomy, aligned with the broader goals of safe, efficient, and infrastructure-free mining automation.

6 Conclusions

Deliverable D4.2 demonstrated a comprehensive set of functionalities required for high-accuracy autonomous operations at the mine face, advancing both perception and planning capabilities for confined underground environments. We developed a behavior-driven motion planning system that guides the deployer robot from a shared map location to the mine face autonomously, based solely on onboard perception. Once in proximity, the robot uses normal vector estimation from LiDAR data to perform final orientation and alignment, ensuring safe and repeatable positioning for drilling or inspection tasks.

A VLM-based magnesite detection pipeline was also introduced, capable of identifying ore features from RGB imagery, representing an interpretable and generalizable approach to onboard semantic scene understanding. Finally, we explored the use of radar-based odometry to improve localization resilience under degraded visual conditions a critical capability for sustained autonomy in dusty, dark, or dynamically changing environments. Together, these contributions support the broader goal of transitioning from simulation to real-world autonomy, enabling complex underground tasks to be performed with minimal human supervision and no dependency on external infrastructure.

7 References

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